
DIVYANG INFORMATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Divyang information System is used for Person with disability. it is windows application software and it is developed for Social Welfare office and NGO'S. To send Applicable Benefits Detail information through SMS.The Divyang information Systemprovides GUI for to reduce paper work of Social Welfares with accuracy ,speed ,less operational time, easy to manage over manually writing data entry on paper system. The application will be installed on the user computer system which runs windows OS. It intends to provide an interface to the user who will require a user id and password to carry out the process.

In present state no software present at all, Manual creation of list of eligible person for that benefits, and For getting all information DIVYANG person go to Taluka or District level Social Welfare offices for many times, many days therefore people waste time, money.Also most important he/she is Handicapped, he/she can't move easily one place to another it's very uncomfortable experience. By using Divyang information System many problems of PwD are solved. Also all detailed information of Benefits Divyang information System is sent to PwD Residential Address through Various electronic media and mobile communication. Also Social welfare office or NGO Can make Report of PwD according to as per need.

KEYWORDS: Divyang Person, NGO, Social welfare office, Government Benefits, SMS.

I. INTRODUCTION**1.1 Existing system :**

Data Entry on Paper System:

No Software present at all., in Social Welfare office for entering the data of Divyangs persons. Still they entering the data on paper by writing.

When Divyang person comes first time to Social Welfare office to getting BUS PASS for Concession in bus tickets. And other concession at that time Social Welfare entering the data of Divyang persons on paper by writing manually.

Entering the data manually on paper by writing, it is not efficient because of it is time consuming. if any mistake in writing then ,it is not easy to remove from paper.

Also it not properly. If writing officer is change then hand writing problem is occurs.

There is no proper data Base available in computerized manner.

When any new scheme announced by Government then making the list of eligible person it is very complex part while data on paper because there are thousands of Divyang persons and Inform them. Also they not able to inform Divyang person what type of required documents, where they contact. Because of improper database .

For getting all information DIVYANG person go to District level Social Welfare offices for many TIME and many DAYS .

Also most important he/she is **Handicaped ,he/she don't move easily one place to another.**

1.2 Proposed System

DIVYANG INFORMATION System:

DIVYANG INFORMATION Software is used for Divyang Persons. it is windows application software and it is developed for Social Welfare office and NGO'S.

The DIVYANG INFORMATION software provides GUI for To reduce paper work of Social Welfares with accuracy ,speed ,less operational time, easy to manage over manually data entry on paper system.

Proper Data Base is required for Social Welfare office to save data properly and in computerized manner.

For get information of Divyang person on a single click.Also make list of eligible person for particular scheme on a single click.

The application will be installed on the user computer system which runs windows OS. It intends to provide an interface to the user who will require a user id and password to carry out the process. Apart from that, the application would support strong user authentication and quick retrieve data from database.

WHY GUI and Proper Data Base required for Social Welfare Office :

No Software present at all., in Social Welfare office for entering the data of Divyangs persons. Still they entering the data on paper by writing.

Therefore they required GUI for Data Entering to data base, if they want delete any unwanted data. If proper Data Base available they can get any information of divyangs person on single click. Also they can list eligible person on single click, **Social Welfare office can send scheme information through SMS to DIVYANGS PERSONS by using mobile company SMS facility** by providing proper data base to mobile company. also reduce work load of Social Welfare office.

II. Scope of Proposed System:

The Benefits will directly received by the NGO.

Hardware Requirement:

- RAM : 1GB
- HDD : 180GB
- PROCESSOR : Dual Core or Above

Software Requirement:

- Operating System : Microsoft XP/7/8/10.
- Front end Software : JAVA swing.
- Net Beans ID : 6.9.1 or above.
- Back end : Oracle database 10g or more

DIAGRAM:

Implementation Block diagram

WORKING:

The application will be installed on the user computer system which runs windows OS.

It intends to provide an interface to the user who will require a user id and password to carry out the process.

All detail Information DivyangInformation Software is send To Divyangs Residential Address through Various Electronic Media and Mobile communication.

This software can be readily used by non-programming personal avoiding human handle chance of errors.

Social welfare officer or NGOs can easily enter the Divyangs information to database for further processing.

Eligible Person can get Information through SMS.

APPLICATIONS:

- It is used by social welfare office and Government.
- It is useful for NGO'S.
- It is useful for Divyang Person.

CONCLUSION:

The Divyang Information software is very useful for Social Welfare office. It is very efficient as compared to manual paper work writing system. Software is user friendly. It is very easy to access. Proper Data Base is required for Social Welfare office to Save data properly and in computerized manner, this software compete all requirements By using this Software get information of Divyang person on a single click. Also make list of eligible person for particular scheme on a single click

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